

Facile synthesis of glycosyl β -lactam from glycosyl β -amino esters

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Abstract : In addition to the wide range of pharmacological activities associated with β -lactams, their importance as synthetic intermediates in organic synthesis has been widely recognized. A series of glycosyl β -lactam of promising chemotherapeutic values has been developed from corresponding β -amino esters in good yield under mild reaction condition.

Keywords : Carbohydrate, glycosyl β -lactams, 2-azetidinone, β -amino ester, intramolecular cyclization.

Introduction

2-Azetidinones, commonly known as β -lactams, are well known heterocyclic compounds associated with wide range of biological activities¹. Activity of known antibiotics such as penicillins, cephalosporins and carbapenems are attributed to the presence of 2-azetidinone ring in them². Beside the antibacterial activity³, recent discoveries of other biological activities, such as anti-

hyperglycemic⁴, antihyperlipidemic⁵, CNS activity⁶, tryptase inhibitory⁷, human leucocyte elastase inhibitory⁸, anti-inflammatory⁹, vasopressin via antagonist¹⁰, anticancer activity¹¹, cholesterol absorption inhibitors¹² and enzyme inhibitors¹³ have renewed the interest in chemistry and biology of 2-azetidinone pharmacophore and has given impetus to these studies (Fig. 1). Therefore, recent years have seen a resurgence of interest in the development of stereoselective methodologies.

Fig. 1. Some β -lactam based antibiotics.

The most common synthetic method for β -lactam is Staudinger's ketene-imine reaction which is carried out either thermally or photochemically using acid chlorides in the presence of NEt_3 α -diazoketones as ketene precursors¹⁴. Later on several valuable modifications of this reaction is well documented in literature¹⁵⁻¹⁸. Lindler *et al.* modified the methods for stereoselective photochemical reaction of diazoketones with the imines for *trans*-arranged 4-aryl/cinnamoyl substituted β -lactams¹⁶, Sharma and Bhaduri for the synthesis of *cis*-*N*-2-hydroxyethyl-2-azetidiones using phenoxyacetic acid in presence of benzenesulfonyl chloride¹⁷ and Shindo and co-workers for the cycloaddition of lithium ynolates to *N*-sulfonyl imines¹⁸ are some of the representative examples. In another way, the intramolecular cyclization of β -amino acid activated by PhP(O)Cl_2 results for the formation of β -lactam¹⁹. Marchand Group successfully developed (3*S*, 4*S*)-1-benzhydryl-3-[(5*R*)-10-hydroxyethyl]-4-acyl-2-azetidiones starting from (2*R*,3*R*)-*cis*-2,3-epoxybutanoate²⁰. Durham-Miller have cyclized β -hydroxy hydroxamates through N1-C4 bond closure under Mitsunobu reaction condition²¹. The formation of 3-hydroxy-2-azetidiones in a reversible photocyclization of phenylglyoxamides of enantiomerically pure α -amino acid methyl esters is reported²². A series of (+)-4-acetoxy-3-hydroxyethyl-2-azetidione²³ is known, where fused tricyclic hydrindene-azetidiones have been obtained from 2-acyl-*N*-(2,2-diphenyl-1-ethyl)-*N*-alkyl-acetamides²⁴. Although a number of useful methods for the synthesis of β -lactam is well-known, however development of eco-friendly approach under mild reaction condition is still need of time. In the present manuscript, we have described a practical synthetic approach for an easy access of glycosyl β -lactam starting from easily available D-glucose.

Results and discussion

Carbohydrates are valuable scaffolds in drug discovery and development as they act as cell surface receptors as well as signaling molecules for molecular recognition and other cellular processes. Besides this good water solubility, optimum pharmacokinetics and low toxicity are the key features which make it a very useful moiety to be used in drug discovery process²⁵. Evident bioactive properties of β -lactam prompted us to synthesize carbohydrates based bioactive molecules. We have synthesized a series of glycosyl β -lactam from corresponding glycosyl β -amino ester. The synthetic route commenced with glycosyl olefinic ester, (1*R*,2*R*,3*S*,4*R*)-ethyl-(3-*O*-benzyl-1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-1,4-pentofuranose-4-yl)-hept-5-enoate (**1**) derived from commercial available D-glucose using a number of known high-yielded multiple steps²⁶. This ester was converted to the glycosyl β -amino ester by 1,4-conjugate addition of amine in presence of $[\text{NMM}]^+[\text{HSO}_4]^-$ as catalyst (Scheme 1).

The resulting glycosyl β -amino esters are proven to have anti-tubercular^{27a} and DNA topoisomerase activities^{27b}. Also, the corresponding glycosyl amino acid has successfully been utilized as organo catalyst for the asymmetric version of Aldol reaction of aromatic aldehydes with acetone²⁸. Moreover, this scaffold is very useful for the synthesis of various biologically active compounds in both solution phase synthesis as well solid phase combinatorial synthesis²⁹⁻³². Some representative examples developed in Tripathi Group^{29,30}, Lucknow and other lab³¹⁻³³ are depicted in Fig. 2. The interesting pharmacological properties of glycosyl β -amino ester garnered our attention to synthesize a series of glycosyl β -amino esters from glycosyl olefinic ester (1*R*,2*R*,3*S*,4*R*)-ethyl-(3-*O*-benzyl-1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-1,4-pentofuranose-4-yl)-hept-5-enoate upon reaction with different amines. Since past few decades, the room temperature ionic liquids (RTILs) show an enhanced performance in a number of

Scheme 1. Synthesis of glycosyl β -amino esters (**2a-1**).

Fig. 2. Glycosyl β -amino ester as a precursor of various biologically relevant molecules.

syntheses involving carbohydrates, when compared to the conventional organic solvents owing to their attractive features, viz. simple handling, high yield, less reaction time, benign environmental character, ease of synthesis and excellent recyclability³⁴. Therefore, we have investigated the conjugate addition of different amines to olefinic ester **1** with the aid of ionic liquid $[\text{NMM}]^+[\text{HSO}_4]^-$ ³⁵, where the short reaction time and excellent reaction yield is the remarkable feature (Table 1).

Structures of synthesized glycosyl β -amino esters were established through spectroscopic analyses (IR, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR). IR spectra of amino esters (**2a-h**) exhibited a common strong characteristic absorbance peak in the range of $3400\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the presence of $-\text{NH}$ group in the compounds. Absorption peaks corresponding to $-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{CH}_2$ stretching appeared in the range of $3000\text{--}2870\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The presence of a strong absorption peak from the region of $1730\text{--}1750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ substantiates the presence of ester group in the molecule. The ^1H NMR spectrum of **2a** shows peaks for five aromatic protons as multiplet at δ 7.33–7.25 ppm. The anomeric peak of furanose ring was appeared at δ 5.94 ppm as doublet (J 3.6 Hz), whereas other peaks observed at δ 4.72 (d, J 12 Hz), 4.64 (d, J 3.6 Hz), 4.46 (d, J 12 Hz), 4.22–4.07 (m), 3.91 (d, J 2.7 Hz) and 3.58 (m) ppm

were correspond to OCHaPh , 2- H , OCHbPh , 4- H , OCH_2 , 3- H and 5- H respectively. The peaks for 6- H and NCH were observed as multiplet in the range of δ 3.36–2.16 ppm, while characteristic $-\text{NH}$ peak was observed as broad singlet at δ 1.63 ppm. The two single peaks for methyl group of isopropylidene were appeared at δ 1.48 and 1.32 ppm. The peaks for three protons of ester's methyl and four protons for propyl ring were observed as triplet and multiplet at upfield value at δ 1.24 and 0.39–0.35 ppm, respectively. The ^{13}C NMR spectra of **2a** gave a characteristic downfield signal for carbonyl carbon at δ 171 ppm. The signals observed between δ 136.9–127.9 were correspond to six Ar-C. The quaternary carbon of isopropylidene appeared at 111.5 ppm, whereas furanoses ring carbon; C-1, C-2, C-4 and C-3 were found at δ 104.8, 81.8, 81.7 and 81.5 ppm respectively. The peaks for $\text{CH}_2\text{PhOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$, C-5 and C-6 were appeared respectively at δ 71.5, 60.3, 54.2 and 36.2 ppm. The NCH carbon, isopropylidene carbon, OCH_2CH_3 and two methylene carbons of cyclopropyl ring appeared at δ 28.0, 26.7, 26.2, 14.2, 7.3 and 5.6 ppm respectively.

Our strategy for the synthesis of glycosyl β -lactam was carried forward with the hydrolysis of glycosyl β -amino ester to glycosyl β -amino acid followed by intramolecular cyclization. The developed glycosyl β -amino

Table 1. Synthesized glycosyl β -amino esters (**2a-l**)

Entry	Amine	Glycosyl β -amino ester (2a-l)	Diastereomeric ratio	Yield (%)
1	Cyclopropyl amine		80 : 20	90
2	Cyclohexyl amine		80 : 20	89
3	<i>n</i> -Butyl amine		80 : 20	90
4	$\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_7\text{NH}_2$		78 : 22	87
5	$\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{15}\text{NH}_2$		80 : 22	84
6	Furfuryl amine		80 : 20	88
7	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$		79 : 21	92
8	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$		78 : 22	95

9		80 : 20	90	
10		85 : 15	89	
11		85 : 15	90	
12		80 : 20	86	

esters (**2a-h**, major isomers) were first hydrolyzed with LiOH in methanol-water at 0 °C to room temperature to give the corresponding glycosyl β -amino acids (**3a-h**) in 84–95% yields. Then, the intramolecular cyclization of the resulting glycosyl β -amino acids (**2a-h**) under the me-

diation of 2-chloro-1-methylpyridinium iodide (Mukaiyama reagent) in the presence of triethyl amine in dichloromethane at 25 °C (the reported Dhavale's protocol)³³ afforded glycosyl β -lactams (**4a-h**) in 80–85% yields (Scheme 2). The developed glycosyl β -lactams of likely

Scheme 2. Synthesis of glycosyl β -lactams (**4a-h**).

to have promising fundamental scaffolds for antibiotic activity and are depicted in Table 2.

All the developed compounds (**4a-h**) were characterized on the basis of their spectroscopic data and analyses.

Table 2. Synthesized glycosyl β -lactams (**4a-h**)

Entry	Glycosyl β -amino ester (2a-h)	Glycosyl β -lactam (4a-h)	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1		3	82	
2		3	85	
3		3	84	
4		3	82	
5		3	83	
6		3	80	
7		3	82	

8

2h

4h

3

81

IR spectrum of compound **4a** did not exhibit the characteristic absorption peak of -NH group in the range of 3400–3300 cm^{-1} indicating the absence of -NH group. The ^1H NMR spectra exhibited aromatic protons at δ 7.32–7.25 ppm as multiplet. The 1-*H*, 2-*H* and 3-*H* of furanose ring appeared as doublet at δ 5.98 (J 3.9 Hz), 4.63 (J 3.6 Hz) and 4.21 ppm (J 3.3 Hz) respectively, while 4-*H* was seen as dd at δ 4.22 ppm. Two benzylic protons were observed as doublet at δ 4.63 and 4.49 ppm. The peaks correspond to 5-*H* and 6-*H* were observed as doublet and double doublet at δ 3.66 and 2.81 ppm respectively. The C-*H* of cyclopropyl ring adjacent to *N*-atom appeared as doublet (J 14.4 Hz) at δ 2.35 ppm

while four protons, two CH_2 of cyclopropyl ring were observed as triplet at 0.65 ppm (J 12.0 Hz). In ^{13}C NMR spectrum, carbonyl carbon appeared at δ 167.3 ppm, while the six Ar-*C* were appeared in the range of δ 136.9–127.9 ppm. The quaternary carbon of isopropylidene ring and four furanose ring carbons (C-1 to C-4) along with benzylic carbon were appeared in the range of δ 111.5–71.5 ppm. The signals of C-5, C-6 and NCH< were observed at δ 50.0, 36.2 and 32.3 ppm, respectively. The two methyl carbons of isopropylidene ring and methylene carbons of cyclopropyl ring appeared at δ 26.6, 26.2, 7.9 and 6.5 ppm, respectively.

Fig. 3a. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **2a**.

Fig. 3b. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound 4a.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have synthesized a series of glycosyl β -amino esters with the aid of ionic liquids in short span of time. On hydrolysis, the resulting glycosyl β -amino acid on treatment with 2-chloro-1-methyl pyridinium iodide in presence of triethyl amine has successfully been utilized for an easy access of corresponding glycosyl β -lactams. The mild reaction condition, high reaction yields in short reaction time, easy in handling, and moreover use of less expensive and easily available nontoxic reagents makes the protocol a practical and facile route for β -lactams. These compounds may themselves show high biological activity or may be utilized as scaffolds for synthesis of potential chemotherapeutic agents.

Experimental

Ethyl-(3-O-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5-cyclopropylamino-1,2-O-isopropylidene)- α -D-gluco and β -L-ido-heptofuranuronate (2a) :

A solution of (1*R*,2*R*,3*S*,4*R*)-ethyl-(3-*O*-benzyl-1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-1,4-pentofuranose-4-yl)-hept-5-enoate **1** (3.60 g, 10.33 mmol, dissolved in 15 mL EtOH),

cyclopropyl amine (0.716 mL, 10.33 mmol) and $[\text{NMM}]^+[\text{HSO}_4]^-$ in catalytic amount (5 mmol %) was magnetically stirred at room temperature for 20 min. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the syrup thus obtained was dissolved in ethyl acetate (100 mL) and washed with H_2O (2×25 mL). The organic layer was separated and dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure to get crude product which was subjected to flash column chromatography (SiO_2) using 20% EtOAc in *n*-hexane as eluent. The major isomer was found in pure form, whereas minor isomer was contaminated with major isomer. Therefore, the characterization data of only major isomer is presented. Yield : 90% (diastereomeric ratio, 80 : 20); IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 3350 ($-\text{NH}$), 2956 and 2918 (CH_3 and CH_2 stretching), 1730 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.33 (m, 5H, Ar-*H*), 5.94 (d, J 3.6 Hz, 1H, 1-*H*), 4.72 (d, J 12 Hz, 1H, $-\text{OCH}_A\text{Ph}$), 4.64 (d, J 3.6 Hz, 1H, 2-*H*), 4.46 (d, J 12 Hz, 1H, $-\text{OCH}_B\text{Ph}$), 4.22–4.07 (m, 3H, 4-*H* and $-\text{OCH}_2$), 3.91 (d, J 2.7 Hz, 1H, 3-*H*), 3.58 (m, 1H, 5-*H*), 3.36–2.16 (m, 3H, $-\text{NCH}$ and 6-*H*), 1.63 (bs, 1H, *NH*), 1.48 and 1.32 [each s, each 3H, $>\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$,

6H], 1.24 (t, J 7.1 Hz, 3H, $-\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 0.39–0.35 (m, 4H, CH_2 's) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 171.8 ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$), 136.9, 128.5, 128.1, 127.9 (Ar-C), 111.5 [$>\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$], 104.8 (C-1), 81.8 (C-2), 81.7 (C-4), 81.5 (C-3), 71.5 (OCH_2Ph), 60.3 (OCH_2), 54.2 (C-5), 36.2 (C-6), 28.0 (NCH), 26.7 and 26.2 [$>\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$], 14.2 (OCH_2CH_3), 7.3 and 5.6 ($2 \times \text{CH}_2$'s) ppm.

General procedure for synthesis of 1,2-O-isopropylidene-3-O-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5-(N-alkylamino)- β -L-ido-heptofuranuronic acid (3a-h) :

To an ice cooled solution of β -L-ido- β -amino ester (1 mmol) in methanol-water (10 mL, 4 : 1) was added lithium hydroxide monohydrate (6 mmol) at 0 °C. The mixture was brought to 25 °C, stirred for 2.5 h and neutralized to pH 7 by addition of 0.5 M KHSO_4 . Methanol was evaporated and residue was extracted with chloroform (3×15 mL), the combined chloroform layer was washed with water, dried with anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to give a pale yellow solid which on purification by column chromatography (chloroform-methanol = 9 : 1) afforded β -L-ido-heptofuranuronic acid.

General procedure for synthesis of 1,2-O-isopropylidene-3-O-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5,7-(N-alkylimino)- β -L-ido-sept-1,4-furan-7-ulose (4a-h) :

To a suspension of 2-chloro-1-methylpyridinium iodide (1.10 mmol, 1.1 equ.) and Et_3N (2.20 mmol, 2.2 equ.) in dry dichloromethane (5 mL) at 25 °C was added a solution of β -L-ido-heptofuranuronic acid (1.00 mmol, 1.0 equ.) in dry dichloromethane (2 mL) dropwise. The solution was stirred at 25 °C for 2 h and water (2 mL) was added. The reaction mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (3×10 mL), the organic layer was dried on anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to give a thick liquid which on column purification (*n*-hexane-ethyl acetate = 8.5 : 1.5) afforded the β -L-ido- β -lactam.

1,2-O-Isopropylidene-3-O-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5,7-(N-cyclopropylimino)- β -L-ido-sept-1,4-furan-7-ulose (4a) :

It was obtained by the reaction of 1,2-O-isopropylidene-3-O-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5-(*N*-cyclopropylamino)- β -L-ido-heptofuranuronic acid (0.40 g, 1.06 mmol) with 2-chloro-1-methylpyridinium iodide (0.297 g, 1.16 mmol) in presence of Et_3N (0.325 mL, 2.33 mmol) in dry dichloro-

methane in 82% yield as white solid; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 1752 (C=O), 1378, 1060; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.32–7.25 (m, 5H, Ar-*H*), 5.98 (d, J 3.6 Hz, 1H, 1-*H*), 4.63 (d, J 3.6 Hz, 1H, 2-*H*), 4.63 (d, J 11.7 Hz, 1H, $-\text{OCH}_A\text{Ph}$), 4.49 (d, J 12.3 Hz, 1H, $-\text{OCH}_B\text{Ph}$), 4.22 (t, J 3.6 Hz, 1H, 4-*H*), 4.21 (d, J 3.3 Hz, 1H, 3-*H*), 3.66 (d, J 3.9 Hz, 1H, 5-*H*), 2.25 (dd, J 14.4 and 4.8 Hz, 2H, 6-*H*), 2.35 (d, J 14.4 Hz, 1H, $-\text{NCH}<$), 1.45 and 1.37 [each s, each 3H, $>\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$, 6H], 0.65 (t, J 12.0 Hz, 4H, $2 \times \text{CH}_2$ of cyclopropyl) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 167.3 (C=O), 136.9, 128.4, 128.0, 127.9 (Ar-C), 111.5 [$>\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$], 104.7 (C-1), 81.8 (C-2), 81.7 (C-4), 81.5 (C-3), 71.5 ($-\text{OCH}_2\text{Ph}$), 50.0 (C-5), 36.2 (C-6), 32.3 (NCH<), 26.6 and 26.2 [$>\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$], 7.9 and 6.5 ($2 \times \text{CH}_2$ of cyclopropyl) ppm.

1,2-O-Isopropylidene-3-O-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5,7-(N-cyclohexylimino)- β -L-ido-sept-1,4-furan-7-ulose (4b) :

It was obtained by the reaction of 1,2-O-isopropylidene-3-O-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5-(*N*-cyclohexylamino)- β -L-ido-heptofuranuronic acid (0.50 g, 1.19 mmol) with 2-chloro-1-methylpyridinium iodide (0.335 g, 1.31 mmol) in presence of Et_3N (0.365 mL, 2.62 mmol) in dry dichloromethane in 85% yield as white solid; IR (KBr) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 1755 (C=O), 1375, 1058; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.32–7.24 (m, 5H, Ar-*H*), 5.98 (d, J 3.6 Hz, 1H, 1-*H*), 4.65 (d, J 11.7 Hz, 1H, $-\text{OCH}_A\text{Ph}$), 4.60 (d, J 3.6 Hz, 1H, 2-*H*), 4.34 (d, J 12.0 Hz, 1H, $-\text{OCH}_B\text{Ph}$), 4.08 (t, J 3.3 Hz, 1H, 4-*H*), 3.86 (d, J 3.9 Hz, 1H, 5-*H*), 3.78 (d, J 2.7 Hz, 1H, 3-*H*), 3.49 (s, 1H, NCH<), 2.80 (dd, J 4.8 and 14.7 Hz, 1H, 6- H_A), 2.35 (d, J 14.4 Hz, 1H, 6- H_B), 1.93 (d, J 10.2 Hz, 2H, $2 \times \text{CH}_A$ of cyclohexyl), 1.64 (m, 2H, $2 \times \text{CH}_B$ of cyclohexyl), 1.45 and 1.33 [each s, each 3H, $>\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$, 6H], 137–1.07 (m, $3 \times \text{CH}_2$ of cyclohexyl); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 169.3 (C=O), 136.1, 128.7, 128.6, 124.8 (Ar-C), 111.5 [$>\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$], 105.7 (C-1), 81.6 (C-2), 81.0 (C-4), 78.9 (C-3), 71.5 ($-\text{OCH}_2\text{Ph}$), 49.1 (NCH<), 45.7 (C-5), 30.1 (C-6), 29.7, 26.9, 25.6 and 25.1 [$>\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$], 22.4 and 21.7 ($5 \times \text{CH}_2$) ppm.

1,2-O-Isopropylidene-3-O-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5,7-(N-n-butylimino)- β -L-ido-sept-1,4-furan-7-ulose (4c) :

It was obtained by the reaction of 1,2-O-isopropylidene-3-O-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5-(*N*-*n*-butylamino)- β -L-ido-heptofuranuronic acid (0.40 g, 1.02 mmol) with 2-chloro-

1-methylpyridinium iodide (0.285 g, 1.12 mmol) in presence of Et₃N (0.312 mL, 2.24 mmol) in dry dichloromethane in 84% yield as white solid; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 1751 (C=O), 1370, 1065; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.34–7.25 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 5.96 (d, *J* 3.6 Hz, 1H, 1-H), 4.62 (d, *J* 11.7 Hz, 1H, -OCH_APh), 4.60 (d, *J* 3.6 Hz, 1H, 2-H), 4.50 (d, *J* 12.0 Hz, 1H, -OCH_BPh), 4.23 (t, *J* 3.3 Hz, 1H, 4-H), 3.96 (d, *J* 3.9 Hz, 1H, 5-H), 3.64 (d, *J* 2.7 Hz, 1H, 3-H), 3.45 (m, 2H, NCH₂-), 2.80 (dd, *J* 4.8 and 14.7 Hz, 1H, 6-H_A), 2.45 (d, *J* 14.4 Hz, 1H, 6-H_B), 1.63 (m, 2H, NCH₂CH₂-), 1.45 and 1.33 [each s, each 3H, >C(CH₃)₂, 6H], 131–0.98 (m, 5H, -CH₂CH₃) ppm; ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 169.3 (C=O), 136.5, 128.6, 128.0, 127.9 (Ar-C), 111.5 [>C(CH₃)₂], 104.7 (C-1), 81.8 (C-2), 81.7 (C-4), 81.5 (C-3), 71.5 (-OCH₂Ph), 54.0 (C-5), 48.2 (NCH₂), 36.2 (C-6), 29.9 (CH₂CH₂CH₃), 26.6 and 26.2 [>C(CH₃)₂], 20.3 and 14.1 (CH₂CH₃) ppm.

1,2-O-Isopropylidene-3-O-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5,7-(N-n-octylimino)- β -L-ido-sept-1,4-furan-7-ulose (4d) :

It was obtained by the reaction of 1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-3-*O*-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5-(*N*-*n*-octylamino)- β -L-ido-heptofuranuronic acid (0.50 g, 1.11 mmol) with 2-chloro-1-methylpyridinium iodide (0.313 g, 1.22 mmol) in presence of Et₃N (0.341 mL, 2.45 mmol) in dry dichloromethane in 82% yield as white solid; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 1757 (C=O), 1372, 1065; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.32–7.25 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 5.95 (d, *J* 3.6 Hz, 1H, 1-H), 4.64 (d, *J* 11.7 Hz, 1H, -OCH_APh), 4.61 (d, *J* 3.6 Hz, 1H, 2-H), 4.52 (d, *J* 12.0 Hz, 1H, -OCH_BPh), 4.65 (t, *J* 3.3 Hz, 1H, 4-H), 3.98 (d, *J* 3.9 Hz, 1H, 5-H), 3.84 (d, *J* 2.7 Hz, 1H, 3-H), 3.25 (m, 2H, NCH₂-), 2.82 (dd, *J* 4.8 and 14.7 Hz, 2H, 6-H_A), 1.63–1.33 (m, 18H, 6 \times CH₂ of octyl amine and 6H, >C(CH₃)₂], 0.92 (t, 3H, -CH₂CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 168.3 (C=O), 136.5, 128.5, 128.1, 127.9 (Ar-C), 111.7 [>C(CH₃)₂], 105.2 (C-1), 81.9 (C-2), 81.6 (C-4), 81.5 (C-3), 71.5 (-OCH₂Ph), 54.0 (C-5), 49.2 (NCH₂), 36.2 (C-6), 29.9 (CH₂CH₂CH₃), 30.4, 30.2, 29.5, 29.1, 27.5 (5 \times CH₂ of octyl amine), 26.6 and 26.2 [>C(CH₃)₂], 21.3 and 14.2 (CH₂CH₃) ppm.

1,2-O-Isopropylidene-3-O-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5,7-(N-hexadecylimino)- β -L-ido-sept-1,4-furan-7-ulose (4e) :

It was obtained by the reaction of 1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-

3-*O*-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5-(*N*-*n*-hexadecylimino)- β -L-ido-heptofuranuronic acid (0.60 g, 1.07 mmol) with 2-chloro-1-methylpyridinium iodide (0.300 g, 1.17 mmol) in presence of Et₃N (0.327 mL, 2.35 mmol) in dry dichloromethane in 83% yield as white solid; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 1751 (C=O), 1370, 1065; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.31–7.25 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 5.97 (d, *J* 3.6 Hz, 1H, 1-H), 4.66 (d, *J* 11.7 Hz, 1H, -OCH_APh), 4.62 (d, *J* 3.6 Hz, 1H, 2-H), 4.46 (d, *J* 12.0 Hz, 1H, -OCH_BPh), 4.33 (t, *J* 3.3 Hz, 1H, 4-H), 3.96 (d, *J* 3.9 Hz, 1H, 5-H), 3.78 (d, *J* 2.7 Hz, 1H, 3-H), 3.15 (m, 2H, NCH₂-), 2.75 (dd, *J* 4.8 and 14.7 Hz, 1H, 6-H_A), 2.55 (d, *J* 14.4 Hz, 1H, 6-H_B), 1.58–1.33 (m, 32H, 13 \times -CH₂ of hexadecyl amine and 6H, >C(CH₃)₂], 0.90 (t, 3H, -CH₂CH₃); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 168.9 (C=O), 137.5, 128.9, 128.6, 128.2, 128.0, 127.8 (Ar-C), 111.7 [>C(CH₃)₂], 104.7 (C-1), 81.7 (C-2), 81.5 (C-4), 81.3 (C-3), 71.3 (-OCH₂Ph), 54.0 (C-5), 48.2 (NCH₂), 36.2 (C-6), 30.5, 29.9, 29.6, 29.7, 29.4, 27.5 (13 \times CH₂), 26.6 and 26.2 [>C(CH₃)₂], 22.5 and 14.1 (CH₂CH₃) ppm.

1,2-O-Isopropylidene-3-O-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5,7-(N-2-phenylethylimino)- β -L-ido-sept-1,4-furan-7-ulose (4g) :

It was obtained by the reaction of 1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-3-*O*-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5-(*N*-2-phenylethylamine)- β -L-ido-heptofuranuronic acid (0.50 g, 1.13 mmol) with 2-chloro-1-methylpyridinium iodide (0.318 g, 1.25 mmol) in presence of Et₃N (0.347 mL, 2.49 mmol) in dry dichloromethane in 82% yield as white solid; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 1748 (C=O), 1385, 1062; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.32–7.25 (m, 10H, Ar-H), 5.94 (d, *J* 3.6 Hz, 1H, 1-H), 4.71 (d, *J* 11.7 Hz, 1H, -OCH_APh), 4.65 (d, *J* 3.6 Hz, 1H, 2-H), 4.43 (d, *J* 12.0 Hz, 1H, -OCH_BPh), 3.95 (t, *J* 4.8 and 3.3 Hz, 1H, 4-H), 3.87 (d, *J* 2.7 Hz, 1H, 3-H), 3.60 (d, *J* 3.9 Hz, 1H, 5-H), 3.47 (t, *J* 3.6 and 4.2 Hz, 2H, -NHCH₂CH₂Ph), 2.86 (t, *J* 8.1 and 6.6 Hz, 2H, 6-H), 2.33 (t, *J* 4.2 and 8.7 Hz, 2H, -NHCH₂CH₂Ph), 1.48 and 1.33 [each s, each 3H, >C(CH₃)₂, 6H] ppm; ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 167.6 (C=O), 137.2, 133.4, 132.5, 132.3, 132.3, 132.2, 132.1, 128.9, 128.7, 128.5, 128.4 and 128.2 (Ar-C), 112.0 [>C(CH₃)₂], 104.7 (C-1), 83.0 (C-2), 82.0 (C-4), 81.3 (C-3), 71.5 (-OCH₂Ph), 53.4 (C-5), 45.0 (NCH₂CH₂Ph), 37.8 (C-6), 37.4 (NCH₂CH₂Ph), 26.6 and 26.2 [>C(CH₃)₂] ppm.

1,2-*O*-Isopropylidene-3-*O*-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5,7-(*N*-benzylimino)- β -*L*-ido-sept-1,4-furan-7-ulose (**4h**) :

It was obtained by the reaction of 1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-3-*O*-benzyl-5,6-dideoxy-5-(*N*-benzylamino)- β -*L*-ido-heptofuranuronic acid (0.46 g, 1.08 mmol) with 2-chloro-1-methylpyridinium iodide (0.302 g, 1.18 mmol) in presence of Et₃N (0.326 mL, 2.36 mmol) in dry dichloromethane in 81% yield as white solid; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1750 (C=O), 1381, 1065; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.70–7.26 (m, 10H, Ar-*H*), 5.95 (d, *J* 3.6 Hz, 1H, 1-*H*), 4.71 (d, *J* 11.7 Hz, 1H, -OCH_APh), 4.65 (d, *J* 3.6 Hz, 1H, 2-*H*), 4.43 (d, *J* 12.0 Hz, 1H, -OCH_BPh), 4.15 (d, *J* 14.1 Hz, 1H, -NHCH_APh), 4.13 (d, *J* 14.4 Hz, 1H, -NHCH_BPh), 3.97 (t, *J* 3.3 Hz, 1H, 4-*H*), 3.87 (d, *J* 2.7 Hz, 1H, 3-*H*), 3.60 (d, *J* 3.9 Hz, 1H, 5-*H*), 2.25 (t, *J* 4.2 and 8.7 Hz, 2H, 6-*H*), 1.48 and 1.33 [each s, each 3H, >C(CH₃)₂, 6H] ppm; ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 171.6 (C=O), 136.8, 133.0, 132.0, 131.9, 131.9, 131.8, 131.7, 128.5, 128.3, 128.1, 128.0 and 127.8 (Ar-C), 111.6 [>C(CH₃)₂], 104.7 (C-1), 83.0 (C-2), 82.0 (C-4), 81.3 (C-3), 71.5 (-OCH₂Ph), 53.4 (C-5), 47.3 (NCH₂Ph), 35.8 (C-6), 26.6 and 26.2 [>C(CH₃)₂] ppm.

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